

Short name	Unclear accounting of BECCS (negative emissions)	Long name	Lack of clarity where (which sub-sector) BECCS is reported in GHG inventories
Geographical scope	All regions, International		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>Engineered greenhouse gas removals need to be included in national accounting and reporting, otherwise there is little incentive to do them. While the voluntary carbon removal market is growing as companies are willing to pay to offset their emissions, without a legal basis and standards for measuring or calculating CO₂ removals, there is little certainty or incentive for companies with existing biogenic CO₂ emissions to invest in capturing and storing them.</p> <p>The EU Climate Law allows for engineered greenhouse gas removals to be counted in its inventory, but it is unclear whether this is the case in national law</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also based on stakeholder inputs)	The UK Energy Bill ¹ includes a provision to amend the Climate Change Act 2008 ² so that engineered greenhouse gas removals can be counted – previously “removals” would only be counted if they came from land-use, land-use change and forestry.		
Other issues this affects	- Accounting Readiness		
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UK Parliament; (2021): Energy Bill, https://bills.parliament.uk/bills/3311, London, United Kingdom. • The National Archives; (2008): Coroners and Justice Act 2009, https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2008/27/contents, London, United Kingdom. 		

¹ <https://bills.parliament.uk/bills/3311>

² <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ukpga/2008/27/contents>